

Research Article

Physico-Chemical Parameters of Rainwater samples obtained in a Suburban Town in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Rainwater is a source of water for bathing, washing, drinking purposes. The uses could be reduced due to its bad condition or state. Air pollution could cause the quality of water to deteriorate, which may be as a result of natural and anthropogenic activities. This paper is the outcome of a 12-month study (June 2018-July, 2019) of rainwater samples collected at Owode, a suburban town located in Ondo State, Nigeria. Physico-chemical properties of the rainwater samples were determined using standard methods of analyses. The results obtained in triplicates were subjected to statistical analysis. The mean results obtained were: Total Dissolved Solids - TDS (21.25 mgL⁻¹), temperature (29.08°C), pH (6.75), Electrical Conductivity – EC (43.20 μS/cm), Free CO₂ (21.83 mgL⁻¹), acidity (230.3 mgL⁻¹), alkalinity (34.50 mgL⁻¹), Cl⁻ (13.33 mgL⁻¹), SO₄²⁻ (19.83 mgL⁻¹), NO₃⁻ (9.57 mgL⁻¹), Ca²⁺ (0.78 mgL⁻¹), Mg²⁺ (0.63 mgL⁻¹), and Na⁺ (0.30 mgL⁻¹). The statistical results indicated that there were correlations between the matrixes. The results when compared with international standard limits, it was observed that our results were lower depicting good quality water in terms of the physicochemical properties, which can be useful for drinking and washing.

Keywords: Rainwater, Physico-chemical composition, drinking purposes, pollution, anthropogenic activities.

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Introduction

Water has many uses throughout the universe, one of them is drinking. In Africa, especially Nigeria poverty has an influence on the type or availability of water for drinking. These have caused a major health concern due to the effects on human and animal health. According to Yasin *et al.*, (2015), over 80% of the diseases recorded were attributed to poor sanitation and polluted water. WHO (2011a) reported about 4 billion cases of diarrhea/year, most homes who depended on streams, rivers, and other flowing waters are usually at disadvantage during the summer periods due to the dryness of water from the sources. In the alternative, shallow wells are dug which also run dry. Most homes cannot afford the sinking of boreholes, but rainwater is harvested until it is needed.

Rainwater provides relieves in terms of availability for major purposes. It is one note that rainwater if not contaminated by the atmospheric pollutants, is believed to be pure (Mehta, 2011). Subramani and Devaanandan (2015) reported that rainwater has the power to dissolve pollutants through a phase change, therefore, rainwater is a major cleansing process of gases, particulate matter, and metals in the atmosphere through dry and wet depositions (Subramani and Devaanandan, 2015; Akoto *et al.*, 2011).

Owode is a suburb town near Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. It is known for housing the Airport. The inhabitants are mostly farmers. There is an incessant tree falling, burning of biomass and vegetation. The small town is surrounded by mild traffic due to the traffic on the expressway and the road leading to the Airport.

The quality of living and non-living things depends on air and water qualities (Abulude, 2018a). An assessment of water and air quality is an integral function of Owode air quality evaluation. Over the years, rainwater researches are undertaken worldwide due to cases of environmental pollution (Akoto *et al.*, 2011; O'Hogain *et al.*, 2011; Cerqueira *et al.*, 2014). However, no work has been reported on the physicochemical composition of rainwater in Owode. Since pollution is a general concern, an in-depth quality of the rainwater within this vicinity is necessary. The monitoring of this part of Ondo State is important due to the high traffic, farming activities, burning of biomass, and the possibility of the effect of the Airport on the quality of rainwater harvested in the locality. To this effect, there is a need to investigate some changes and other characteristics of atmospheric pollution in this area. The present report is on the physicochemical composition of the precipitate in Owode. This is needed because of the anthropogenic and non-

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anthropogenic activities in this small area. The objective of the study is to examine the levels of atmospheric pollution in Owode by determining the physico-chemical properties of the rainwater. The results obtained, will significantly add to the very limited knowledge present on rainwater quality in Akure and Ondo State in general.

Literature Review

Physic-chemical Parameters

The physical and chemical parameters of interest in this study are odour, taste, colour, pH, temperature, EC, TDS, EC, Free CO₂, Acidity, Alkalinity, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, and Na⁺. A short review of these is presented in the paper.

Odour

One of the good properties of water is the odour. Rainwater should be devoid of odour. Foul odour in water will render it useless for man, animals, and aquatic life because of the toxic effects it could have on them. A foul odour experienced in drinking water is an issue that must be prevented or eliminate (VanWyngarden, 2016). Most of the smell experienced in water is not a confirmation of the presence of a harmful contaminant, it could infer that the drinking water is not clean. When it rains, there is the possibility of contaminations before collection or harvesting within the distance covered from the sky to the storage tanks. According to VanWyngarden (2016), over 316 contaminants are found in water supplies throughout the U.S, among them are, sulfur, sewage, fish and wet dog odours. To remove the taste and colour in the water a point-of-use (POU) water filtration system is recommended.

Colour

Natural rainwater is pure water and so it should be colourless. If perchance, it has colour, it could be due to ions, suspended matter, weeds, plankton, and acids like humic and fulvic acids. There are permissible limits for the usefulness of the water. If these are exceeded, then the water will be rendered useless. Colour should be removed before it can be useful for industrial and general applications. Coloured water causes adverse effects on human health and the aquatic environment. Colourless water may provide evidence that there is some form of contamination (State Water Resources Control Board, accessed 2019).

Taste

The term residue refers to an amount of floating suspended, settable and dissolved solids present in water. The residue may affect water quality. Water having high contents of

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total residue has an elevated density and reduced oxygen solubility. Such water is inferior in terms of palatability. It is on a note that high TDS in water may alter the taste, odour, and colour of rainwater (Mastoi *et al.*, 2014). Salt and sweet tastes are experienced in water example a salty taste could be due to the presence of a high concentration of naturally occurring minerals such as calcium or iron, or an imbalance in water's alkaline or pH levels and sweet taste could have chloride ions and/or sulfates in the supply (VanWyngarden, 2016). POU systems are recommended in conjunction with a 1 micron activated carbon block filter certified for lead and cyst removal, which have a solid carbon rod to remove contaminants including lead, cysts, chlorine, sediment, taste, odor and organic contaminants (VanWyngarden, 2016).

Temperature

This plays an important function in the control of biological and physic-chemical parameters in water. Temperature is known to have a strong correlation between ecological activity. High temperature renders microbes in aquatic systems inactive. By this action, the quality of the water lasts long (Paul *et al.*, 1991; Mastoi *et al.*, 2014). Temperature plays a very important role in wetland dynamism affecting the various parameters such as alkalinity, salinity, dissolved oxygen, electrical conductivity, etc. In an aquatic system, these parameters affect the chemical and biological reactions such as solubility of oxygen, carbon-di-oxide-carbonate-bicarbonate equilibrium, increase in metabolic rate and physiological reactions of organisms (Mastoi *et al.*, 2014).

EC

EC is the ability of water to transmit electric current. EC is a good instrument to assess the quality of water (Murugesan, 2006). According to Mehta (2011), high EC concentration in water is not good enough because this will aid a high amount of salts dissolved in water. High dissolved salts will affect the quality (not suitable for drinking) of the water sample. Again, the high salinity of the water prevents water absorption from surrounding soil, which affects the plant growth negatively. High salt in water impels the crop to use more energy to absorb water from the soil (Mastoi *et al.*, 2014).

TDS

This parameter explains the quality of water because TDS in water originates from different sources like sewage natural sources, the nature of pipe used in conveying water, and agricultural runoff. In the case of the quality of water, contamination could be due to the washing of pollutants from the atmosphere into the storage tank. The TDS include carbonate, bicarbonate, chloride, sulphate, phosphate, nitrate, calcium, magnesium,

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sodium, organic ions and other ions. TDS affects the taste of drinking water if present at levels above the WHO recommended level. High values of TDS in groundwater are generally not harmful to human beings but a high concentration of these may affect persons, who are suffering from kidney and heart diseases. Water containing high solid may cause laxative or constipation effects. According to Sasikaran *et al.* (2012), potable water should not contain more than 1000mg L⁻¹ of total dissolved solids (TDS).

pH

The effect of pH on the chemical and biological properties of liquids makes its determination very important. It is one of the most important parameters in water chemistry and is defined as $-\log(H^+)$, and measured as intensity of acidity or alkalinity on a scale ranging from 0-14 (Mehta, 2011).

Nitrates

Nitrates are the most oxidized forms of nitrogen and the end product of the aerobic decomposition of organic nitrogenous matter. The significant sources of nitrates are chemical fertilizers from cultivated lands, drainage from livestock feeds, as well as domestic and industrial sources. Acid rain forms when sulphur dioxide and nitrogen oxides combine with water. NO_x dissolves in rainwater in the atmosphere, to produce nitric acid (HNO₃), when this dilute acid falls to the ground when it rains and produces nitrate in ponds. Road transport is a major source of these pollutants. Agricultural activities, human and animal excreta aid nitrate to get into the water (WHO, 2011b).

Phosphates

They occur in solution in particles or as detritus. They are essential for the growth of organisms and a nutrient that limits the primary productivity of the water body. Inorganic phosphorus plays a dynamic role in aquatic ecosystems; when present in low concentration is one of the most important nutrients, but in excess along with nitrates and potassium, it causes algal blooms (Limgis, 2001).

Sulphates

Soluble in water, it imparts hardness with other cations. Sulphate causes scaling in industrial water supplies, and odour and corrosion problems due to its reduction to hydrogen sulphate. It can be calculated by turbidometric method (Limgis, 2001).

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Free Carbon-Di-Oxide

The important source of free carbon-di-oxide in surface water bodies is mainly from respiration and decomposition by aquatic organisms (Limgis, 2001). It reacts with water partly to form calcium bicarbonate and in the absence of bicarbonates gets converted to carbonates releasing carbon-di-oxide.

Acidity and Alkalinity

Acidity or alkalinity, which was measured by pH-meter, has great ecological importance because the behavior of ions and organic compounds is directly related to the pH-value.

Cl⁻

The presence of chlorides in rainwater can be deduced to the dissolution of salts and pollutants to form chloride ion. A high concentration of the ion in rainwater may indicate pollution (Limgis, 2001). High concentrations of chloride in rainwater could have a serious effect on crops and metallic pipes.

Mg²⁺

Magnesium is abundant in the earth's crust (8th in abundance of the elements). It is present in natural waters due to the dissolution of rocks. It has a function on the crop's nutrients (Chlorophyll). A high quantity of Mg²⁺ reduces the usefulness of water for domestic use, imparts bad tastes to water. The unpleasant effects of water can be reduced by softening, reverse osmosis, and electro dialysis.

Ca²⁺

Calcium is one of the most abundant in water, this as a result of dissolution and deposits of dolomite, limestone, gypsum, and others. It contributes to the hardness (total) of water. Presence of calcium ion at a high concentration in water forms harmful scales in pipes, boilers, and utensils.

Na⁺

Sodium-ion is a natural and abundant constituent in water. This is soluble in water, rainwater inclusive. The concentration of Na⁺ ranges from low (in surface water) to relatively high in groundwaters, and highest in marine waters (Limgis, 2001).

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Materials and Methods

Figure 1: Map of the study area

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Fig 2: Pictorial diagram of the sampler used for the collection of rainwater sample

The collected sample was subjected to immediate analyses before treatments and storage. The pH was determined using a pen-type pH meter (PH-009 (I)) made in China, TDS, Temperature, and EC were obtained using a pen-type TDS and EC meter (EZ-1) made in China, and colour, odour, taste, free CO₂, acidity, alkalinity, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, and Na⁺ of samples were subjected to appropriate determinations, using standard methods of analyses (Limgis, 2001).

Data obtained (basic descriptions and multivariate analyses) were generated in triplicates and analyzed, using Minitab 16 Statistical Software. The percentage contributions of the physicochemical properties were determined by Excel 2016 software.

Results and Discussion

It was noted by direct observation that all the water samples were found colourless and clear. Similarly, a direct inspection of the samples for odour was done and found that samples were odourless. These observations explain that the water samples were pure and that they have little or none of the pollutants that cause the colour, odour, and taste changes.

Table 1 depicts the basic description of the physicochemical parameters. pH ranged from 5.70-9.20 acidic to alkaline range. The pH value of water is an indication of how acidic or basic the water is on the scale of 0 to 14. The highest TDS in summer was observed as 88 mg L⁻¹ while the lowest was 2 mg L⁻¹. The values were lower than the WHO and SON value of 600 mg L⁻¹ purity (devoid contaminants). The highest value of alkalinity was reported during November (summer period) was 354 mg L⁻¹ which could be due to the presence of decay and decomposition of vegetation and insect. The Free CO₂ ranged between 12.00 and 50.00 mg L⁻¹ with a mean of 21.83 and standard deviation of 11.52

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Table 1: Basic Description of the results from July 2018 – June 2019

Variable	Mean	StdDev	CoefVar	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Colour	Clear	-	-	-	-	-	-
Taste	Tasteless	-	-	-	-	-	-
Odour	Odourless	-	-	-	-	-	-
TDS	21.25	24.60	115.74	2.00	88.00	2.08	4.82
Temperature	29.08	1.93	6.63	27.00	33.00	1.05	0.12
pH	6.95	0.93	13.39	5.70	9.20	1.12	2.34
EC	43.20	49.20	113.88	4.00	176.00	2.05	4.69
Free CO ₂	21.83	11.52	52.76	12.00	50.00	1.84	2.76
Acidity	230.30	54.20	23.54	165.00	354.00	1.04	1.30
Alkalinity	34.50	7.87	22.81	23.00	46.00	-0.03	-1.22
Cl ⁻	13.33	5.00	37.48	6.00	20.00	0.04	-1.58
SO ₄ ²⁻	19.83	4.06	20.49	14.00	28.00	0.52	0.10
NO ₃ ⁻	9.57	2.87	29.97	6.00	16.00	0.91	0.80
Ca ²⁺	0.78	0.14	17.31	0.56	1.00	0.04	-0.94
Mg ²⁺	0.63	0.09	14.69	0.46	0.78	0.01	-0.44
Na ⁺	0.30	0.08	25.28	0.18	0.42	-0.04	-1.06

StdDev – Standard Deviation, CoefVar – Coefficient of Variation

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Table 2: Comparison of our study with standards and results from other countries

Parameters	Our Study	References				
		WHO (2011)	SON (2007)	Brazil (Cerqueira <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	India (Umerfaruq and Solanki 2015)	Italy (Lelpo <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Colour	-	-	-	-	-	-
Taste	-	-	-	-	-	-
Odour	-	-	-	-	-	-
TDS (mg L ⁻¹)	2.00-88.00	600	600	-	958-1246	294-6620
Temp (°C)	27.00-33.00	-	-	-	18-27	-
pH	5.70-9.20	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	4.4-6.9	8.2-9.3	6.8-7.2
EC (µS/cm)	4.00-176.00	1000	1000	3.4-35.2	3.1-3.54	0.45-7.9
Free CO ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)	12.00-50.00	-	-	-	-	-
Acidity (mg L ⁻¹)	165.00-354.00	-	-	-	-	-
Alkalinity (mg L ⁻¹)	23.00-46.00	-	-	-	194-274	-
Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	6.00-20.00	250	250	5.8-67.6	98-103	44.3-2765
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	14.00-28.00	50	50	3.3-72.7	7.5-8.7	0.2-67.0
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	6.00-16.00	250	250	4.7-39.8	-	7.3-632.2
Mg ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.46-0.78	-	-	1.6-153	31-34	8.0-240
Ca ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.56-1.00	150	-	3.5-239	30-46	17-480
Na ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.18-0.42	-	-	5.3-70.4	41-55	20-1450

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Figure 2: Contributions of the cations and anions in the rainwater samples

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Table 3: Correlation coefficient of the Physico-chemical parameters

	TDS	Temp	pH	EC	Free CO ₂	Acidity	Alkalinity	Cl ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺	Na ⁺
TDS	1												
Temp	0.4	1											
pH	0.4	0.01	1										
EC	0.5	0.4	0.6	1									
Free CO ₂	0.9	0.6	0.8	0.9	1								
Acidity	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	1							
Alkalinity	0.9	0.6	0.6	0.9	0.7	0.4	1						
Cl ⁻	0.8	0.1	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.2	0.1	1					
NO ₃ ⁻	0.5	0.9	0.9	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.4	1				
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.0	0.4	0.7	0.0	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.8	0.4	1			
Mg ²⁺	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.7	0.9	0.3	0.7	1		
Ca ²⁺	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.4	0.7	0.9	0.6	0.7	0.5	1	
Na ⁺	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.9	0.4	0.1	0.8	0.3	0.9	0.6	0.3	1

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Figure 3: Matrix plot of the physico-chemical parameters

Figure 4: Loading plots of the Physico-chemical parameters

Figure 5: Box plot of the Physico-chemical parameters

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The EC values (4.00 - 176.00 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) were within the 1000 mg L^{-1} limit set by the WHO and SON. The values in this study were significant ($P < 0.05$). The mean acidity values (230.30 mg L^{-1}) were high but below the WHO/SON limits. This could be attributed to the presence of organic matter pollution present during the time of sample collection. Nitrate was relatively low in the water samples, as values ranged from 6 to 16 mg L^{-1} . Nitrate is the most highly oxidized form of nitrogen compounds and is commonly present in groundwater because it is the end product of the aerobic decomposition of organic nitrogenous matter (Akoto *et al.*, 2011). Nitrate values in rainwater samples were below the set limits for drinking water and compared with works reported by Akoto *et al.* (2011) and Lelpo *et al.* (2012) (Table 2). SO_4^{2-} values (14.00 and 28.00 mg L^{-1}) were low, below the WHO, and similar with values obtained by Akoto *et al.*, 2011 (Ghana rainwater), but not comparable to that of Lelpo *et al.*, 2012 (Italy rainwater). Figure 2 shows the percentage of contributions of anions and cation in the water samples. The months of January and February showed that SO_4^{2-} values were 11 and 12 % respectively. The high contributions could be due to the high temperatures within these periods. For Cl^- the highest values were recorded for the months of March (13%), September (12%), and Mg^{2+} (April and August - 10%), Ca^{2+} (October - 11%), Na^+ January - 12%). All these values were obtained during the months with high rainfalls. During these months, there are the probabilities of high dissolutions of these anions and cations from the atmosphere. This study revealed that the physicochemical parameters were within the WHO/SON tolerable limits (Table 2). The low concentrations of the anions and cations could be attributed to the low contributions of anthropogenic factors such as vehicular activities, absence of organic matter, and biomass burning in the location. The concentrations of TDS, Mg^{2+} , and Ca^{2+} showed that the rainwater could be useful for drinking and bathing purposes.

Significant positive correlations were observed between Free CO_2 , pH, and EC ($r=0.9$); Alkalinity, EC ($r=0.9$); Cl^- , pH, EC, and Free CO_2 ($r=0.8$); NO_3^- , Temp., and pH ($r=0.9$); SO_4^{2-} and Cl^- ($r=0.8$); Mg^{2+} and Cl^- ($r=0.9$); Ca^{2+} and Cl^- finally, Na^+ , Free CO_2 , and SO_4^{2-} ($r=0.9$). SO_4^{2-} , Mg^{2+} , EC, and Free CO_2 were positively significant when correlated with chloride. This showed that the same source could be inferred for these elements that were significantly correlated (Egereonu and Nwanchukwu, 2005). The temperature of the water samples was not affected by seasonal variations. High nitrate contents in water have shown in the epidemic of methemoglobinemia in infants (Ibe and Onu, 1998), an outgrowth of algae which can foul the water, and gastric cancer (Siddiqi *et al.*, 1992).

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The matrix plot is the variables that are shown in a diagonal line from top left to bottom right (Figure 3). The physicochemical parameters variables were plotted against each other. The first column was an individual scatterplot of TDS and temperature, with TDS as the X-axis and temperature as the Y-axis. In this graph, scatterplot was replicated in the middle of the top row. Meaning that the boxes on the upper right-hand side of the whole scatterplot were mirror images of the plots on the lower left hand (Abulude *et al.*, 2018b). In the graph, it was shown that there was a correlation between TDS and temperature. The matrix scatters plot also depicted weak correlations between EC and Acidity, and pH and EC. The correlation matrix in Table 3 testifies to this.

In figure 4 loading plot for the data set analysed is shown. There are high loading values for Mg^{2+} , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , TDS, EC and Na^+ on the first component explaining 43% of the total variance, while second component (explaining 18% of the total variable) has strong loadings on NO_3^- .

All the physicochemical properties of the rainwater samples except pH, alkalinity, Cl, Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ and Free CO_2 skewed to the right, which means they are nonsymmetrical (Figure 5). Free CO_2 has its interquartile range in the sample, while TDS, temperature, EC, NO_3^- has its range in the upper quartile. The reason for the skewing to the right was that there were large variations in the values of physicochemical properties recorded in the study. The boxplot is a visual display presents five different statistical tools in a study - the minimum, the lower quartile, the median, the upper quartile, and the maximum. It is an indicator of centrality, symmetry, spread and tail length of the population and sample (Abulude *et al.*, 2018b).

Conclusion

The study revealed that there were significant variations in the physicochemical parameters determined. The results were lower than the set guidelines by WHO and SON. It could be concluded that the water samples have good qualities that are suitable for washing and drinking purposes. However, regular monitoring should be ensured.

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